

DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHARKORLIK ORQALI PASIYA TIZIMINA ISHONCHNI QAYTA QILISH UCHUN MOLIVAVIY INKLUSIYONNI KUSHAYTIRISH

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Annotatsiya. O'tish davridagi iqtisodiyotga ega mamlakatlarda pensiya tizimi asosan davlat nazoratida bo'lib, xususiy sektor ishtiroki minimal darajada qolmoqda. Har qanday islohotlarga qaramay, tizimning samarasizligi va mehnat bozorida keng tarqalgan norasmiylik sababli aholining ushbu tizimga bo'lgan ishonchi pastligicha qolmoqda. Ozarbayjonda o'zini o'zi band qilgan aholining, ayniqsa qishloq va shahar hududlarida, pensiya tizimiga jalb etilishini rag'batlantirish bo'yicha amalga oshirilgan sa'y-harakatlar yetarli darajada samarali bo'lmagan. Ushbu tadqiqot davlat-xususiy sherikchilik (PPP) mexanizmlarini moliyaviy inklyuziyani oshirish va pensiya tizimiga bo'lgan ishonchni tiklashda transformatsion strategiya sifatida o'rganadi. Xalqaro tajriba va so'rovnomalarga tayangan holda, Ozarbayjon pensiya tizimidagi asosiy muammolar – ixtiyoriy ishtirokning sustligi, moliyaviy savodxonlikning pastligi hamda ish haqi solig'iga haddan tashqari bog'liqlik aniqlanadi. Tadqiqot ko'p ustunli yondashuvni ilgari suradi, ya'ni davlat tomonidan qat'iy tartibga solinadigan sharoitda xususiy pensiya jamg'armalari, ish beruvchilar tomonidan moliyalashtiriladigan ixtiyoriy sxemalar va raqamli moliyaviy xizmatlar integratsiyasini taklif qiladi. Shuningdek, xususiy sektor ishtirokini rag'batlantirish, oshkora boshqaruvni ta'minlash va norasmiy mehnat qiluvchi aholiga xizmat ko'rsatishda fintech vositalaridan foydalanish zarurligi ta'kidlanadi. Mazkur yondashuv orqali Ozarbayjon yanada inklyuziv, diversifikatsiyalashgan va barqaror pensiya tizimini shakllantirishi mumkin. Tadqiqot natijalari pensiya islohoti va moliyaviy inklyuziya bilan bog'liq strukturaviy muammolarga duch kelayotgan rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlar uchun muhim siyosiy tavsiyalarni taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Davlat-Xususiy Sherikchilik, Moliyaviy Inklyuziya, Norasmiy Iqtisodiyot, Davlat Tizimlariga Ishonch, Ijtimoiy Himoya, Xususiy Pensiya Jamg'armalari, Iqtisodiy Siyosat

Аннотация. В странах с переходной экономикой пенсионная система, как правило, находится под контролем государства, а участие частных структур в ней минимально. Несмотря на продолжающиеся реформы, уровень общественного доверия к системе остается низким, это в основном из-за предполагаемой неэффективности и высокого уровня неформальной занятости на рынке труда. В Азербайджане меры по расширению охвата пенсионной системы, в частности среди самозанятого населения в сельских и городских районах, оказались недостаточно результативными. В данном исследовании рассматривается потенциал государственно-частного партнёрства (ГЧП) как инструмента преобразования пенсионной системы, направленного на повышение финансовой включённости и восстановление доверия населения. На основе анализа международного опыта и данных опросов выявлены ключевые недостатки азербайджанской пенсионной системы как бы низкий уровень добровольного участия, недостаточная финансовая грамотность и чрезмерная зависимость от взносов, привязанных к заработной плате. Предлагается комплексный подход, включающий развитие частных пенсионных фондов, добровольных программ, спонсируемых

работодателями, а также внедрение цифровых финансовых услуг под надёжным государственным контролем. Особое внимание уделяется стимулированию участия частного сектора, обеспечению прозрачного управления и применению финтех за решений для вовлечения работников неформального сектора. Такой подход позволит создать более инклюзивную, устойчивую и диверсифицированную пенсионную систему. Результаты исследования могут быть полезны для стран с аналогичными экономическими и институциональными вызовами.

Ключевые слова: Государственно-Частное Партнёрство, Финансовая Инклюзивность, Неформальная Экономика, Доверие К Государственным Институтам, Социальная Защита, Частные Пенсионные Фонды, Экономическая Политика

Abstract. *The pension system is primarily under state control, with minimal involvement from private entities in transitional economies. Despite ongoing reforms, public trust in the system is low, largely due to perceived inefficiencies and the informality prevalent in the labor market. In Azerbaijan, efforts to promote and sustain self-employment coverage for both rural and urban populations have proven insufficiently effective. This study explores the potential of public-private partnerships (PPPs) as a transformative strategy to improve financial inclusion and restore trust in the pension system. By analyzing international experiences and survey data, the research identifies critical deficiencies within the pension framework of Azerbaijan, including weak voluntary participation, inadequate financial literacy, and excessive dependence on payroll tax contributions. It advocates for a multi-pillar approach that integrates private pension funds, employer-sponsored voluntary schemes, and digital financial services, all under firm public regulation. The paper highlights the necessity of encouraging private sector involvement, fostering transparent governance, and utilizing fintech to engage informal workers. Through this approach, Azerbaijan could develop a more inclusive, diversified, and resilient pension system. The findings provide policy insights for emerging economies facing similar structural challenges in pension reform and financial inclusion.*

Key words: *Public-Private Partnerships (PPP), Financial Inclusion, Informal Economy, Trust in Public Institutions, Social Protection, Private Pension Funds, Economic Policy*

Introduction

Financial inclusion is broadly defined by the World Bank (2025) as the availability and usage of affordable financial products and services by individuals and businesses [13]. Several studies (Demirgüç-Kunt et al., 2018; Allen et al., 2016) have shown that enhancing access to formal financial services can positively influence long-term savings habits, sustain retirement security, and increase participation in pension schemes [1 and 2]. In the context of developing and emerging economies, where informal employment and income volatility are prevalent, financial exclusion remains a significant barrier to universal pension coverage.

Trust in pension institutions significantly influences voluntary participation, particularly in systems that incorporate partially funded or voluntary elements. As noted by Schwarz and Arias (2014), factors such as governance quality, benefit predictability, transparency, and perceptions of fairness play a crucial role in shaping trust [6]. In Azerbaijan, the prevailing low trust in the pension system is attributed to perceptions of ineffective fund management and the inadequacy of retirement benefits in relation to contributions. Many individuals express concerns about whether they will reach retirement age, as they rely on government pensions but are uncertain about their sufficiency for a decent living. The primary worry is whether they will even see the retirement age. The burden of pension contributions falls mainly on the working

population, who experience significant stress and fatigue, leading to health issues and a shorter lifespan compared to those who do not work and rely on government support. Consequently, there is a prevailing belief in Azerbaijan that pensions are not a guaranteed outcome for future as individuals contribute to the pension fund with fear that they may not live long enough to benefit personally, while others might receive disproportionate advantages.

Pension in Azerbaijan

In 2024, Azerbaijan’s pension system supports approximately 1.1 million beneficiaries, of whom 64% receive old-age pensions, 23.6% receive disability pensions, and 12.4% are pensioners due to the loss of a family breadwinner. Compared to 2020, the overall number of pensioners has declined by 13.7%. This reduction includes a 5.4% decrease in old-age pension recipients, a substantial 32.8% drop in disability pensioners, and a 13.7% decline among those receiving pensions due to the loss of a family head (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Number of pensioners in Azerbaijan

Source: Made by author based on the data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan [8].

The decline in the number of pensioners in Azerbaijan can be attributed to various factors, depending on the specific category of beneficiaries. In the case of old-age pensioners, the gradual increase in the retirement age for women initiated from 2017, has played a significant role. According to current policy in Azerbaijan, the retirement age for women increases by six months each year in July, aiming to equalize the retirement age of men and women at 65 by 2026. As of 2024, the retirement age stands at 65 for men and 64 for women [4]. This progressive adjustment has naturally slowed the entry of new female beneficiaries into the pension system, thereby contributing to the steady decline in the number of old-age pensioners since 2020.

The significant 32.8% reduction in the number of disability pensioners in Azerbaijan is primarily attributed to the implementation of stricter regulations governing the eligibility and assessment of disability status. Historically, the absence of rigorous oversight allowed some individuals to obtain disability benefits through unofficial or inaccurate means. In recent years, enhanced regulatory scrutiny and the establishment of more stringent verification procedures

have revealed numerous cases of ineligible recipients, including individuals receiving pensions based on falsified or exaggerated disability claims. Following thorough reviews conducted by medical and legal commissions, these cases have been systematically identified and terminated, with financial damages recovered through judicial processes. In Azerbaijan, the acquisition and retention of disability status are now governed by clear and enforceable legal frameworks. Article 320 of the Criminal Code outlines penalties for the use of falsified documents to obtain pension benefits. Offenders may face fines ranging from 1,000 to 2,000 manats, community service of 240 to 300 hours, correctional labor for up to one year, or imprisonment. These measures have significantly contributed to enhancing the integrity of the disability pension system and reducing fraudulent claims. [5]. These regulatory changes, while aimed at improving oversight and curbing fraudulent claims, have also given rise to public discontent. Many perceive the measures not as a targeted effort to eliminate abuse, but rather as a broad reduction in social support. This perception has contributed to a decline in trust toward the disability pension system, with some viewing the reforms as an unjustified general cut rather than a necessary correction. According to former Minister of Labor and Social Protection, Sahil Babayev, approximately 500 million AZN was saved during the first ten months of 2021 as a result of these stricter controls [3]. While highlighting the scale of previous inefficiencies and the fiscal impact of the reforms it also has fueled public skepticism about the motives of government as suggesting that cost-cutting than over social justice.

The Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Labour and Social Protection of Population of Azerbaijan for 2021–2025, outlines the *development of the insurance-pension system* as a key policy direction, signaling the commitment of government to reform and modernize the national pension framework during the planning period [9, p. 4]. The insurance-pension system offers a more inclusive and sustainable approach to financing social security compared to the traditional Pay-As-You-Go (PAYG) model. Under this system, employers contribute on behalf of employees into individual accounts, and the benefits are directly tied to the amount contributed. A major advantage of this model is the strong correlation between contributions and benefits, which enhances transparency and trust in the system. Additionally, because funds are pooled, invested, and managed over time, the system is less vulnerable to demographic shifts, particularly the rising ratio of retirees to working-age individuals. When contributions are carefully managed, properly funded, and diversified, the mandatory social insurance scheme can become significantly more inclusive, financially resilient, and equitable, aligning with long-term policy goals.

The social protection system in Azerbaijan has had a significant positive impact on reducing absolute poverty. As noted by ILO (2016), old-age and disability pensions played a particularly important role, with the universal nature of the system ensuring that its poverty-alleviating effects remained strong and effective over time [10, p. 6].

While retirement savings may originate from both public and private sources, the underlying motivations behind them differ. Public savings are primarily aimed at building reserves to sustain national social security systems, serving the broader societal interest [6, p. 118]. In contrast, private savings are generally individual-focused, intended to supplement retirement income through personal or employer-sponsored pension plans. Within this framework, public-private partnerships (PPPs) play a crucial role in enhancing inclusiveness and efficiency in the social protection system. Public savings represent a deductive approach, addressing collective welfare through standardized mechanisms, while private savings reflect a more inductive logic, tailored to individual needs and preferences. Despite their different

approaches, both components ultimately converge toward the shared objective of ensuring income security.

	2020		2021		2022		2023		2024	
	E	U	E	U	E	U	E	U	E	U
Age	15,6	84,3	15,6	84,	16,	83,	18,	81,	19,	80,
	6	4	4	7	3	1	9	3	7	
Disability	11,2	88,7	12,3	87,	12,	87,	16,	84,	17,	82,
	2	8	7	8	2	0	0	6	4	
Lost the head of the family	1,02	98,9	1,5	98,	1,8	98,	1,9	98,	2,3	97,
	8	5	5	2	1,9	1	2,3	7		
Total pensioners	12,6	87,3	13,0	87,	13,	86,	15,	84,	16,	83,
	5	5	0	8	2	5	5	8	2	

Table 1. Employment and unemployment conditions of pensioners in Azerbaijan, %

Source: Made by author based on the data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan [7].

The proportion of employed individuals among pensioners, particularly old-age pensioners, has shown a gradual increase in Azerbaijan. As of 2024, 19.3% of all old-age pensioners are engaged in formal employment (Table 1). Notably, the share of employed disability pensioners has also risen significantly. While in 2020 only 11.2% of individuals receiving disability pensions were employed, this figure increased to 17.6% by 2024. This shift is largely attributed to government policies aimed at incentivizing the employment of persons with disabilities, including tax reductions for employers who hire them. Similarly, employment among recipients of pensions due to the loss of a family breadwinner has increased when compared to 2020. This trend is supported by relatively flexible policy measures, in particular, the state continues to provide survivor pensions if a child of the deceased breadwinner remains enrolled in formal education, up to the age of 23. These dynamics represent the structural modifications in pension policy alongside wider initiatives aimed at incorporating vulnerable groups into the workforce.

Financial inclusion aids in retirement readiness, investing, and sound financial decision-making [11, p. 1]. Financial inclusion helps on the removing of retirement inequality with enabling affordable private pension system with impacting retirement soundness.

When private pension schemes are effectively integrated into the broader pension system through PPPs, they may complement rather than displace existing savings, thereby contribute to increase aggregate savings, investment, and inclusive financial development. In recent, growing attention has been directed toward micropensions as retirement savings schemes specifically tailored for individuals at the lower end of the economic spectrum. These schemes are typically managed by microfinance and microinsurance institutions, which promote inclusiveness by facilitating the collection of small, consistent contributions from low-income individuals. However, despite promising potential in micropensions, the growth has been gradual and limited, largely due to the extended pilot phases required to adapt models to a country’s specific socio-economic context. This includes addressing challenges such as financial literacy, consumer protection, behavioral economics, and the operational sustainability of service delivery.

Advancing micropension models within a PPP framework offers a promising path toward a more inclusive, diversified, and resilient pension system. Countries such as India, Ghana, and several in Latin America have initiated exploratory models [12, p. 13]. However, the sector still requires further innovation and policy support. In this context, PPPs could play a vital role in establishing scalable, inclusive, and sustainable micropension frameworks, especially for informal sector workers.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, the landscape of pension systems in Azerbaijan and beyond is undergoing significant transformation, driven by demographic shifts, economic pressures, and evolving socio-economic needs. The journey towards a more inclusive, sustainable, and trust-inspiring pension framework is complex but crucial for ensuring long-term social and economic stability.

The Azerbaijani experience highlights the delicate balance between necessary reforms and public perception. While stricter regulations have improved system integrity, they have also sparked concerns about social support reduction. This underscores the importance of transparent communication and stakeholder engagement in pension reform processes.

The gradual shift towards an insurance-pension system in Azerbaijan represents a promising step towards greater sustainability and inclusivity. By linking benefits more closely to contributions, this approach has the potential to enhance transparency and build trust. However, its success will depend on effective implementation, robust governance, and ongoing adaptation to changing circumstances.

The role of financial inclusion in supporting retirement readiness cannot be minimised. As studied, access to affordable financial products and services can significantly impact long-term savings habits and pension participation. The emerging field of micropensions, particularly when developed through PPPs, offers an innovative approach to extending pension coverage to underserved populations, including those in the informal sector. However, this transition requires effective planning, policy support, and a commitment to ongoing innovation. The integration of PPPs, could double targeted initiatives to inclusive finance with fulfilling the active role in more resilient and equitable pension system for low income population.

Ultimately, the goal of pension reform should be to develop a system that not only ensures financial security for retirees but also instills confidence in future generations. This requires a holistic approach that addresses not just financial sustainability, but also issues of trust, inclusivity, and adaptability to changing societal needs.

As countries around the world grapple with similar challenges, the lessons learned from experience of Azerbaijan can provide valuable insights. By fostering trust, embracing innovation, and prioritizing inclusivity, countries can work towards pension systems that truly serve the needs of all population, today and in the future.

REFERENCES

1. Allen, F., Demircuc-Kunt, A., Klapper, L., & Martinez Peria, M. S. (2016). The Foundations of Financial inclusion: Understanding Ownership and Use of Formal Accounts. *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 27(1), 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfi.2015.12.003>
2. Demircuc-Kunt, A., Klapper, L., Singer, D., Ansar, S., & Hess, J. (2018). Global Findex Database 2017[La base de datos Global Findex 2017]. In *ideas.repec.org*. The World Bank Group. <https://ideas.repec.org/b/wbk/wbpubs/29510.html>

3. Firuzə , V. (2021). Nazir: “10 ayda əsassız pensiyaların ləğvi nəticəsində 500 milyon manat vəsaitə qənaət edilib” [*Minister: “500 million manats saved as a result of the abolition of unjustified pensions in 10 months”*]. Apa.az. <https://apa.az/az/xeber/senaye-ve-energetika/nazir-10-ayda-esassiz-pensiyalarin-legvi-neticesinde-500-milyon-manat-vesaite-qenaet-edilib-670062>
4. MLSPP. (2017). Yaşa görə əmək pensiyası [*Old-age labor pension*]. Sosial.gov.az; The Ministry of Labour and Social Protection of the Population of the Republic of Azerbaijan. <https://sosial.gov.az/az/fealiyyet/fealiyyet-istiqametleri/pensiya-ve-sosial-sigorta-esasli-muavinetler/pensiya/yasa-gore-emek-pensiyasi>
5. Rüstəmli, B. (2021). Saxta pensiya əlillik düzəldən və alanları hansı cəza gözləyir [*What punishment awaits those who create and receive fake disability pensions?*]. Qaynarinfo.az. <https://qaynarinfo.az/az/saxta-pensiya-elillik-duzelden-ve-alanlari-hansi-ceza-gzleyir-huquqi-serh/>
6. Schwarz, A. M., Arias, O. S., & Zviniene, A. (2014). Inverting Pyramid : Pension Systems Facing Demographic Challenges in Europe and Central Asia. World Bank Publications. <https://www.worldbank.org/content/dam/Worldbank/Feature%20Story/ECA/ECA-Pensions-Report-2014.pdf>
7. SSC. (2025). Number of employed and unemployed pensioners. Stat.gov.az; The State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan . https://www.stat.gov.az/source/healthcare/en/002_1.4en.xls
8. SSC. (2025). Number of pensioners. Stat.gov.az; The State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan . https://www.stat.gov.az/source/healthcare/en/002_1.2en.xls
9. EU Commission. (2022). Twinning Reference: AZ/20/ENI/SO/01/21 (AZ 59). EuropeAid/173613/DD/ACT/AZ. https://www.bmeia.gv.at/fileadmin/user_upload/Zentrale/Europa/EU-Twinning/April-Juni_21/ANNEX_C1_Twinning_Fiche_Pension_reform_docx.pdf
10. ILO. (2016). Universal pensions in Azerbaijan. Social-Protection.org. <https://www.social-protection.org/gimi/gess/Media.action>
11. Marcelin, I., & Sun, W. (2025). Financial inclusion, inequality, and retirement trends among older workers. *Global Finance Journal*, 66(101121), 1–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfj.2025.101121>
12. HelpAge International and the Center for Financial Inclusion. (2015). Aging and Financial Inclusion: An Opportunity. Accion. https://www.fundacionmicrofinanzasbbva.org/revistaprogreso/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/envejecimiento-e-inclusion-financiera_en.pdf
13. World Bank. (2025). Financial Inclusion. World Bank. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/financialinclusion/overview>